

Recommended citation: Nathans - Kelly, T. M., Evans, R., & Hutchison, A. (2020). Maximizing the Engagement Factor for Engineering, Scientific, or Technical Posters: Purpose, Exchange, and Universal/Accessible Design. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1442-1443). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14654422](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654422).

MAXIMIZING THE ENGAGEMENT FACTOR FOR ENGINEERING, SCIENTIFIC, OR TECHNICAL POSTERS: PURPOSE, EXCHANGE, AND UNIVERSAL/ACCESSIBLE

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Conference Key Areas: *Interdisciplinary education, Future engineering skills*
Keywords: *posters, design, accessibility, best practices*

ABSTRACT

Using the online format in a live and interactive manner, this workshop will address—and challenge—the “academic poster” as an information exchange medium for engineering, scientific, and technical work. (We will use the live f2f format provided by the conference, crowd-sourced documents, and polling/word cloud tools in the moment for true interactions.)

The genre of “academic poster” has been long considered to have a “settled” format, firmly grounded in intellectual traditions. Its overall purpose is to highlight the researchers’ work and provide an opportunity for networking with other experts with similar backgrounds or interests. The purpose of this workshop is to re-examine this traditional format, break it apart, and find better ways to meet the differing audiences that will attend poster sessions (whether they are face to face or online events). Despite the plethora of “best practices” guidelines available online or via conference organizers [1], many of us have attended failed poster session events. Mike Morrison, an advocate for billboard-style or Poster 2.0 design, goes as far to say that “poster sessions are usually a dispiriting waste of time for all involved” [2]. Novice poster makers treat the medium as a stand-up, large-form version of lengthy research reports. Experienced poster presenters make similar mistakes. Ineffective visuals, text-heavy practices, and poor design is evident at every conference or gathering. Therefore, the workshop presenters intend to re-route the approach,

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assisting participants to think about this question: “What do you want the audience to do after viewing your poster?”

This highly interactive workshop invites participants into a deep dive that will pull apart the expected norms of the EST poster, challenging creators to entirely reconsider purpose, appeals to specific academic communities [3, 4], universal design/accessibility, design, and more. We will investigate two types of poster sessions: interactive/reciprocal/supported (with speakers present) and static/unsupported (with no speakers present) [1]. As well, due to the nature of a pandemic world, we will address the different ways that poster sessions can be hosted or used for online events.

Participants will learn how to help colleagues and interested experts come away from a poster with action items and collaborations in mind. Based in cognitive research [4-7], multimodal theory [4-7], and learner outcome pedagogies, participants will investigate poster creation by examining communicative context, communicative design, engineering identity, and engineering practice [7].

Additionally, issues of supplementary information dispersal (post-event) and accessibility for disabled attendees will be addressed [8, 9].

Specifically, workshop participants will:

1. analyze, in guided discussion, several poster designs, content, and delivery methods;
2. interact in synchronous “live” groups, assessing the features of poster design and content and tapping into the collective creative intelligence of participants;
3. creating rich descriptions of desired poster features and audience-engagement outcomes;
4. re-imagine and critically assess, in guided groups, on their own poster design and best practices checklist using these rich, curated principles for poster design using the customized sketchbook provided (which will also contain resources and prompt materials for take-aways).

It is desirable that attendees have a future/current/planned poster idea or draft on hand that they can share via guided online breakout room discussion. As well, a smartphone will allow participants to more easily contribute to our online information gathering that results from our discussions about how to re-imagine posters.

Participants will leave with a mature set of workshop materials available immediately online, including a customized sketchbook and sets of resources for poster best practices. Materials will also include the group-sourced outcomes that are generated during the event.